

Title of Presentation	Simplifying the Fitting Procedure in AFM Indentation Experiments on Samples with Finite Thickness.
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Abstract

When testing soft biological samples, such as cells on rigid substrates, using Atomic Force Microscopy (AFM), the equations typically used for data processing are the classical ones derived from Hertzian mechanics. For example, when using conical indenters, the applied force (F) is proportional to h^2 , where h is the indentation depth on the sample. In other words, $F = ch^2$, where, c is a constant that depends on the material properties (Young's modulus and Poisson's ratio) and the cone's half angle [1]. For parabolic (or spherical indenters and small indentation depths) $F = c'h^{3/2}$, where c' is a constant that depends on the material properties and the indenter's radius [2]. In conventional AFM experiments on biological samples the Poisson's ratio is considered equal to 0.5 due to high water content [1, 2]. Therefore, since the parameters c, c' are calculated as fitting constants, the Young's modulus can be easily determined under the condition that the indenter's properties are known. The equations above apply if the sample is assumed to have an infinite depth (or in cases that the sample's thickness significantly larger than the indentation depth). However, in most cases, the experiment does not meet the criterion above, and the substrate has a non-negligible influence on the results. In such cases, appropriate correction functions, expressed as power-law series, have been derived based on the properties of the indenter and whether the sample is bonded to the substrate [1, 2]. When using these correction functions, the force-indentation equations take the general form $F = F_{Hertz}f(h, H)$, where F_{Hertz} denotes the classical equations from Hertzian mechanics, and $f(h, H)$ is the appropriate correction function (where, h is the indentation depth and H is the sample's thickness) [1, 2]. The equations above are complicated, making the fitting process less straightforward. Therefore, the idea is to simplify the fitting process by considering an equivalent force-indentation equation of the form $F = \mu \left(\frac{h}{H}\right)^m$, where, μ, m are constants that depend on the indenter's properties, the material properties and the h/H ratio. The idea is based on considering an equivalent, simple power-law function, for $f(h, H)$ with the same area under the graph and the same maximum value. Using this approach, the force-indentation equation takes a simple power-law form: $F = \lambda(h_{max}, H, E, \nu, \Omega)h^n$, where λ depends on the maximum indentation depth (h_{max}), the sample's thickness (H), the material properties (Young's modulus E and Poisson's ratio ν) and the indenter's properties Ω . In addition, the exponent n depends on the h_{max}/H ratio and the indenter's properties. The exact values of the exponent n and the parameter λ for each indenter and h_{max}/H ratio can be easily determined using the procedure described above, which involves equating the integral and the maximum value of the actual function $f(h, H)$ to those of a simple power-law function. Using this approach, appropriate tables incorporating λ and n parameters can be easily developed, enabling a straightforward power-law fitting for the force-indentation data.

References

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